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THE CAPABILITIES OF VISUAL BASIC FOR APPLICATIONS IN CREATING A DEMONSTRATION AND TRAINING COURSE FOR THE COURSE “PROGRAMMING IN PASCAL”**Vugar Salmanov***Ph.D., assoc. prof.**Department of Informatics The Nakhchivan State University**Azerbaijan Republic, Nakhchivan city,**University campus, AZ7012, Nakhchivan State University*

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Abstract

The article is dedicated to the development of a methodology to teach students how to create multimedia educational programs based on the Visual Basic for Application software environment and use them in the teaching of the Informatics course on the example of learning Pascal programming language technology in the teaching of the Informatics course. The novelty of the research is in the justification of the possibility and effectiveness of using the Visual Basic software environment for the creation of multimedia educational programs and in the development of methodical approaches to their application in the teaching process of informatics. Visual Basic uses many of the same features as other Windows programs. This menu bar is a toolbar that contains buttons to perform the most requested operations, as well as a workspace where the program is formed. Some menus are typical, such as File, Edit, Help and others. One of the elements of the working window is the toolbar, which provides quick access to most of the most frequently used functions. The toolbar or shortcut menu of functions is designed according to the standards used by the latest generations of programs. The form, file and run buttons are placed on the ruler. Most Visual Basic programs contain at least one screen form that contains interface elements and other objects. By placing the images of control objects on the screen form, the user visually controls the process of creating the interface.

Keywords: Pascal, Visual Basic for Application, programming, course.

1. Introduction

Informatization of society is an objectively ongoing process. Its peculiarity is that one of the main activities of society members is the processes related to the collection, storage, processing and transmission of information. In this regard, one of the leading directions in the process of informatization of society is the process of informatization of education, which provides the education sector with methodical and practical tools for the creation and use of information technologies for training and educational purposes.

Determining the rational ways of using computer technology and new information technologies in the teaching process of the school and university posed the problem of psychological and pedagogical justification of the transition of the educational system to new pedagogical technologies.

One of the main issues of informatization of education is the training of future informatics teachers based on the modern requirements of pedagogical science. Currently, there is already some experience in the field of studying the problem of theoretical and methodical training of students of pedagogical universities. Didactic and methodical support of the informatics course of the school and pedagogical university Mirzayeva A. (Mirzayeva, 2019, p. 50-53) Zhaldak M.I. (Zhaldak, 1992) and described in the works of other authors. The work of many researchers is devoted to the problem of training a future informatics teacher who has fundamental knowledge in the field of informatics and computer technologies and the methodology of applying information technologies in the teaching process (Abdurazakov, Dzamykhov, Temirdzhanova, 2014, p.

268-273; Kodzhaspirova, Petrov, 2006; Koropovskaya, Krupoderov, 2009, p. 10-30; Muslimov, Kodirov, 2011, p. 109-112; Polat, Bukharkina, 2008; Polyakova, 2016, p. 86-97; Trainev, Trainev, 2007, p. 9-110; Shikhvarger, 2013, p. 132-136). Some researchers (Robert, 2010, p. 10-22) note the special importance of using the possibilities of multimedia technology to present audiovisual information for educational purposes.

Currently, ways of updating its content are actively being sought in the field of education. The result of this is the renewal of educational standards aimed at the formation of the personality of the future specialist, the introduction of new forms of organization of the educational process. A modern teacher has to work in constantly changing conditions, which in turn requires improvement of his professional qualities. The constant development of pedagogical theory and methodology, the application of new educational technologies to pedagogical practice shows that additional training of modern teachers in the field of pedagogical technologies is necessary (Salmanov, 2022, p. 34-38, (a)).

Interactive classes provide an opportunity for all learners, including passive, shy, as well as students with certain physical or psychological disabilities, to actively participate in the educational process. Even sometimes, a student who answers a question incorrectly in regular classes reacts painfully to the teacher's rebuke in front of other students, and is distressed. In the interactive mode, the teacher can very well explain what the mistakes are and how to correct them by showing the mistakes made by the student individually, not in front of the whole class (Salmanov, 2022, p. 97-103, (b)).

Computer-based learning environments serve as valuable assets to help enhance teacher training and enhance teacher self-regulated learning (Huang, Lingyun & Dias, Laurel & Nelson, Elizabeth & Liang, Lauren & Lajoie, Susanne & Poitras, Eric.,2022).

2. Statement of the problem

Teaching programming technology is one of the components of training in the field of informatics. Recently, the most common programming language is Python. The most suitable language for learning programming is Pascal, so the issue of finding new forms and methods of teaching programming in this language is very relevant.

Existing traditional forms of education in the form of laboratory exercises with the involvement of lecture, practical and educational materials are not enough for good mastery of the learned material. Additional resources are needed to deliver all the intricacies and features of Pascal to great effect.

In Visual Basic (Salmanov, 2017, p. 5-10) linking is done by writing a program, which is usually called a project. The project consists of forms (Form) - areas of the screen (windows) occupied by the program during operation and on the background of which images of controls and indicators are located. Among the latter, the main menu, text fields, text and images, command buttons and others can be mentioned. To each such object, a specific subroutine is added that performs the required function, and the sum of all subroutines determines the work of the created project. By using VBA in the PowerPoint program, it is possible to develop the methodology of a new technology in the organization of education.

3. Content of the multimedia training-demonstration course "Programming in Pascal".

The multimedia training-demonstration course "Programming in Pascal" should cover almost all sections of the Pascal language and should include the

whole range of different forms of presentation of educational material in the form of hypertext, diagrams, drawings, animation and sound (speech) accompaniment. The course should be built on the basis of the menu principle, allowing access to the desired section of the language from any point. Having a menu should allow the teacher to select a section of the study material to display at any time. The program should have a main menu with 4 elements: general features of the language, data types, control structures and dynamic objects. Each of these elements, in turn, should have a sub-menu specifying the corresponding section of the language. In addition, the built-in test module allows individual and frontal testing of knowledge by choosing the sequential test mode (questions are presented one after the other in a predetermined order) or the selective inquiry mode (the order of the presented questions depends on the request).

Movement in a sequence of frames is carried out using buttons located independently or assembled on the control panel (Figure 1). The fact that this or that button is active is reflected by the inversion (color change) of some part of the screen corresponding to the action zone of this button. In short, if any part of the screen reverses its color while moving the "mouse" cursor around the screen, it means that you have reached the control button, call for more detailed information or an example in the form of hypertext, or "jump" to another frame of this article, wherever possible. Such transitions are provided in the frames: "Management structures / branches" - from the first frame to the frames containing information about the Case statement and the If statement; "Control Structures / Loops" - a framework that discusses the implementation of cyclic structures in Pascal for each of the three operators: Repeat, While, For; "Management structures / Procedures and functions" - for each of these structures separately from the framework that characterizes these structures.

Figure 1. Frame links panel

The functions of each button and the main methods of working with this course are described in the help text, which can be called from the frame containing the opening screen of the program. From the same frame, information about the author of this program is called and a transition to the main menu is made.

For ease of use, each frame provides access to the main menu ("Back" button) and sub-menu of the section ("Back" button), transition to the next and previous frames ("<<" ">>" buttons) and exit ("Exit" button)

It is they who help to move freely from one point to another along the course, thereby realizing the interactive capabilities of the program. In addition, a number of buttons are inserted into the control panel and directly into the screen area, providing "service" to the footage: sound playback ("Sound" button), animation

display ("Animation" button) are located on the control panel.

Let's take a closer look at the four sections that make up the main menu of the course.

4. Pascal programming language features

This section consists of a submenu with two items.

Programming languages - defines a programming language, discusses high- and low-level languages, procedural and non-procedural languages, translation and its types (interpretation and compilation), how and when the Pascal algorithmic language was created. A brief description of the Pascal programming system is also given, while working with it, the general appearance of the screen (user interface) is shown, the meaning of the main menu line options and instructions is

revealed (Karimov, Habibullayev, Ibrahimzade, 2010, p. 137-197).

The alphabet of the Pascal algorithmic language, the types of data and variables - reveals the meaning of the concept of "syntax diagram", gives its definition and features of the main parts, construction rules. The structure of the Pascal program is shown, its similarity with the program in the school algorithmic language is noted. When types are given in a Pascal program, information is given about them.

5. Data types in Pascal

Simple Types - This subsection provides a diagram of simple data types with a definition of each. The structure of the data declaration is reviewed - the syntax diagram of the declarations is given with the definitions of all the sections included in the declaration: modules - Uses, labels - Label, constants - Const, types - Type, variables - Var, procedures - Procedure and functions - Function.

Arrays - shows the need to implement this composite type, its definition, a syntax diagram with definitions for each of its components, a general note with explanatory examples, and how variables of this type are described in a Pascal program. Definitions of one-dimensional, two-dimensional (matrix), and multidimensional arrays are also given. The main methods and methods of working with arrays are discussed and examples are given.

String data - here we talk about ways to work with character (Char type) and string (String type) values, the need to implement such types, the differences between one type and another, and character arrays. A general note with examples of the use of these types is provided. String functions are considered: Concat ("combine"), Length (length determination), Pos (position), Copy (fragment cutting) and procedures: Delete (fragment deletion), Insert (fragment insertion), Str (transformation. number to string), Val (string to number conversion). Each procedure and function is accompanied by an example that explains how it works.

Sets - the definition of this composite type, the syntax diagram and the general form of notation with examples of the type itself and variables of this type are given in the corresponding sections of the Pascal program. Operations on sets are considered: assigning a value to a variable of an empty set, giving it a special value using a set constant, union, intersection and difference of sets, as well as comparison of sets (one element of a set is a member of a set), insertion of one set into another, one set into another. insertion, overlap of sets).

Records - this section explains the need to create such a type, gives its syntax diagram and the general form of the record. In the Pascal program, the concept of notation is introduced with options that facilitate the use of variables of this type. The subsection is full of examples to help you understand and master the properties of this type of data and how to work with them.

Files - this subsection contains a syntax diagram and the general form of this type of record. The need to introduce a file type as a means of separating the data itself from the program module is justified. Various types and types of files are considered, including text

files. Basic procedures and methods of working with files are explained: opening files for reading and writing, reading from and writing to a file, defining a file name with a file variable, closing a file.

Pointers - this section completes the discussion of Pascal's various data types and includes the definition of the reference type. Here, the general form of the record is given, the creation of dynamic variables and variables with pointers, operations on pointers, operations on dynamic variables are considered. There is an animation fragment about operations on pointers.

6. Control structures in Pascal

Data input/output - the main operators are considered here, with the help of which data input and output are carried out: Read, Readln (serves for input of information), Write, Writeln (for output of information) procedures. An overview of these procedures is given, the working principles of each of them are shown with examples and with the help of two animation fragments: Read and Readln procedures, Write and Writeln procedures.

Branching - two operators are defined, with the help of which branching is performed in Pascal: If and Case. Syntax diagrams and an overview of each of these operators are given, and similarities and differences between them are shown. Examples of the formation of simple conditions using comparison operations, as well as complex conditions using the logical operations Not, And and Or are considered.

Loops - this section includes an overview of three types of cyclic structures in Pascal - While, Repeat, For statements.

Procedures and functions - here there is a lot of emphasis on the need to create structures such as procedures and functions, they are defined.

7. Dynamic objects in Pascal

Chains - here the need to create a dynamic object like a chain is revealed, the main principles of its construction are mentioned. A typical construction rule for determining a chain is described, the connection of elements in it is shown schematically.

Queues - the definition of the queue, the procedure for specifying the type for its construction, the scheme of combining elements in the queue is given. The main operations on queues are described in detail using animation: creating a queue, viewing (printing) its elements, adding and deleting links.

Stacks - the subsection includes the definition of a stack, a diagram of its connecting elements and a description of the main operations on stacks: formation, insertion of a new one and removal of an existing link, access to the Nth link of the stack.

Decks - this subsection contains the definition of a deck, the connection scheme of its elements, the procedure for specifying a type, and the main operations in decks: transition formation, insertion and deletion.

Trees - contains the definition of a tree data structure along with a schematic representation of the tree. Types of trees are considered: ordered, binary (binary), balanced and search tree.

We can also use the Visual Basic for Application (VBA) environment to create demo-training courses. For this, we can create perfect demonstration-training

courses using VBA in PowerPoint application. Also, subject tests are well received in this environment (Figure 2, 3).

Types in Pascal

Subject

Find Clean up Next slide

Figure 2. Form on the subject.

Types in Pascal

Subject Real

It is the Real type. It takes up 6 bytes of memory

Find Clean up Next slide

After writing Real

Types in Pascal

Subject Integer

It is a Integer type. It takes up 2 bytes of memory

Find Clean up Next slide

After writing Integer

Figure 3. The response form received when typing the subject in the text field

The program for command keys in VBA is as follows:

“Find” button:

```
Private Sub CommandButton1_Click()
If Text1.Text = "Real" Then Label2.Caption = " It
is the Real type. It takes up 6 bytes of memory "
If Text1.Text = "Integer" Then Label2.Caption =
" It is a Integer type. It takes up 2 bytes of memory "
If Text1.Text = "Boolean" Then Label2.Caption =
" It is a Logical type. It occupies 1 byte in memory "
End Sub
```

“Clean up” button:

```
Private Sub CommandButton2_Click()
Label2.Caption = ""
Text1.Text = ""
End Sub
```

“Next slide” button:

```
Private Sub CommandButton5_Click()
SlideShowWindows(1).View.Next
End Sub
```

It is also possible to evaluate the topic with slides prepared in the form of a test (Figure 4).

Question 1

▶ Which language is suitable for primary programming?

Figure 4. Test form

The program codes for the command keys are as follows:

```
Private Sub CommandButton1_Click()
k = 0
n = 0
n = n + 1
MsgBox "False"
SlideShowWindows(1).View.Next
End Sub
```

The code for the second incorrect button is the same.

```
Private Sub CommandButton2_Click()
k = 0
```

```
k = k + 1
```

```
n = 0
```

```
n = n + 1
```

```
MsgBox "True"
```

```
SlideShowWindows(1).View.Next
```

```
End Sub
```

The code for the "Next slide" button:

```
Private Sub CommandButton4_Click()
SlideShowWindows(1).View.Next
End Sub
```

When a right or wrong answer is given, a dialogue window opens and the answer is finalized by pressing the button (Figure 5).

Question 1

▶ Which language is suitable for primary programming?

Figure 5. Form received after correct answer (When the button that says Pascal is clicked)

Question 1

▶ Which language is suitable for primary programming?

Figure 5. Form received after correct answer (When clicking the button that says other words)

8. Conclusions

Within the framework of the use of the Visual Basic for Application programming language, the methodology for creating a demonstration and training course on the "Programming in Pascal" course is given.

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